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Home-Based Mental Health: A Call to Strengthen Family-Based Support for Children

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Abstract

This paper examines the critical role of family-based support in promoting children's mental health by investigating the possible causes of children's poor mental health, early health identification, management, and prevention that can positively affect and prevent the onset of mental disorders. This has become necessary because children's mental health is an integral component of health and well-being, influencing academic, social, and economic outcomes across the lifespan. Since the foundation is the strength of the structure, it is assumed that the seed of poor mental health might have been laid at home in the early years. Child mental health is a significant public

challenge that impacts children's ability to learn, behave, and manage their emotions. The findings of the paper demonstrate that poor mental health among children is a pressing global concern. It emphasises that early home factors, including parental styles and personality, family structure, marital divorce, separation, and other family changes, are primary contributors to the decline in children's mental health. It concludes that children's mental health requires a holistic approach that integrates parents, caregivers, schools, government, and health professionals who should work together to create a nurturing environment that supports their well-being. The paper, therefore, recommends a reorientation programme to ensure interventions in areas like health, education and social protection, such as parenting and whole-school programmes. It calls for societies to break the silence surrounding mental health by addressing stigma, promoting understanding, and taking seriously the experiences of children and young people.

Keywords: Children, Mental Health, Home, Parenting, Family-based Support and Prevention

Introduction

Early life is a crucial period of biological, emotional, and mental development. It is becoming increasingly clear that the origins of many mental health problems lie in childhood, and this can have lasting effects on children's life chances. Children's mental wellness is increasingly becoming a global concern (UN, 2014). Mental health is a basic right and essential for achieving global objectives, including the Sustainable Development Goals (UNICEF, 2021). Mental health exists on a complex continuum, with experiences ranging from an optimal state of well-being to experiencing severe mental health conditions with related suffering and often an important impact on the capacity to carry out daily activities (United Nations Transforming Education Summit, 2022). According to a study done by the World Health Organisation, it was revealed that an estimated 10% and 20% of children worldwide suffer from mental health problems. Depression and anxiety disorders are among the five leading causes of disease burden among children and adolescents (WHO, 2021, cited in Lahti; Korhonen; Sakellari; Notara, & et al, 2023). The study further revealed that, in general, there is a serious failure in the early detection and treatment of mental health problems, and a huge gap exists between those needing mental health services and those receiving them (Cairns and Rossetto, 2019; Purgato, 2020).

Children's mental health is an integral component of health and well-being that influences academic, social, and economic outcomes across their lifespan. Having good mental health means being better able to interact with others, function, cope, and thrive. It has been observed over time that the good mental health of children begins at home. A child's home influences his or her development. Within the home environment, children can be exposed to many stresses that will affect their everyday lives. Children's health and well-being are dependent on the health and well-being of the family unit. A safe and secure home environment could provide a sufficient level of excitement for the child to discover their surroundings while at the same time giving responsive support in stressful situations. Unfortunately, not all children have what they need to support their mental health right from home. Ryan, Farrelly & Ramchandani (2017) emphasised that family factors, including the quality of care that parents provide for their children, can make a huge difference in children's early life pathways, for better or for worse.

The study conducted by Shoval, Chiu, Taylor & Barzilay (2022) revealed that parenting is often described as one of the most complicated life challenges, and the complexity increases in the presence of child developmental and/or mental health conditions. In connection with mental health, children who are deprived of parental care and a secure family environment often become vulnerable to a host of psychological problems and psychiatric disorders. Children may, for example, experience neglect, abuse, violence, aggression, poverty, and poor academic performance. Changes within the family setup, like divorce or separation, can also impact children and young people's mental health. Exposure to an inadequate home environment may put the healthy development of children at risk. For children, these have lifelong consequences for their health and well-being. While there is an emerging body of empirical studies focused on the adverse consequences for the mental health of adults, less attention has been paid to understanding how this global catastrophe is affecting children, not only in terms of learning loss but also for their mental health.

Homes through parenting psychoeducation should be an ideal platform for promoting children's mental health, identifying early signs of mental health concerns, and supporting referrals to community-based mental health services when necessary. The impact of home factors as a major determinant of good children's mental health cannot be overemphasised. Currently, there

is a paucity of universal home-based mental health identification, management, and prevention programmes in countries, including our nation, Nigeria. Therefore, this paper intends to raise awareness regarding the roles of family-based support in promoting children’s mental health and to provide all the necessary and required support within the system where the child grows, encouraging healthy mental and emotional growth. Thereby, addressing the issue of early identification, effective management and prevention strategies for children’s mental health

What is mental health?

Mental health, according to the World Health Organisation (2005), can be defined as a “state of well-being in which every individual realises his or her potential, copes with the normal stresses of life, works productively and fruitfully, and can contribute to her or his community”. The state of your mental health affects your thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. It also affects how you navigate life, relationships, work, school, and other daily activities. The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child commits all countries to promote and protect child and adolescent mental health (World Health Organisation, 2022). It is a basic human right.

The World Health Organisation (2022) revealed from the available study that the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic go far beyond the suffering and death caused by the disease itself. It has disrupted education, mental well-being, and livelihoods, deepened existing inequalities, and weakened past gains. For adolescents, including children, these have lifelong consequences for their health and well-being.

The State of Children's Mental Health Globally

The UNICEF Executive Director released a report, that too many children and young people, rich and poor alike, in all four corners of the world, are experiencing mental health conditions (UNICEF & WHO, 2019). This looming crisis has no borders or boundaries. With half of mental disorders starting before age 14, there is a need for urgent and innovative strategies to prevent, detect, and, if needed, treat them at an early age.”

The State of the World’s Children (2021). Mental health conditions continue to represent a huge burden on children in high- and low-income countries, representing a leading cause of death and disability. The report finds that the risk and protective factors influencing children’s mental health pertain

to three main areas: home and caregiving settings, safety in schools and communities, and large-scale determinants, such as poverty, conflict, and natural disasters.

According to UNICEF (2021), it is estimated that more than 13 per cent of adolescents aged 10–19 live with a diagnosed mental disorder as defined by the World Health Organisation. The cost of mental disorders is not only personal; it is also societal and economic. Notably, children's and adolescent mental health has often been overlooked in global and national health programming. The conference was part of *Leading Minds*, UNICEF's new annual global conference series to highlight major issues affecting children and young people in the 21st century. UNICEF and the World Health Organisation are teaming up with some of the world's leading minds to tackle this growing threat.

Hossain et al (2022) stated that most of the reviews reported a high prevalence of anxiety, depression, sleep disorders, suicidal behaviour, stress-related disorders, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, and other mental health problems. These effects are expected to have adverse impacts on the welfare and mental health of children through sleeping disorders, depression, stress, and anxiety (Hossain et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2021). Mental health conditions, such as childhood epilepsy, developmental disabilities, depression, anxiety, and behavioural disorders, are major causes of illness and disability among young people. Worldwide, 10% of children and adolescents experience a mental disorder, but the majority of them do not seek help or receive care (WHO, 2024).

Poor Mental Health

Poor mental health among children poses a public challenge worldwide. Children and youth in low-and middle-income countries (LMIC) are at greater risk for poor mental health. Parents' psychological problems may lead to negative parenting behaviours, a lack of attention to children's needs, or increased dysfunction within the home. (Elgar et al. 2007; Wilson and Durbin 2010, cited in Kamis, 2020). Adverse circumstances, including poverty, violence, and lack of available psychological treatments, increase their vulnerability (Pedersen, Smallegange, Coetzee, Hartog & et al., 2019). The environments of homeless children are uniquely chaotic, marked by frequent moves, family structure changes, household and neighbourhood

disorder, parenting distress, and lack of continuous services. Despite high rates of service use, mental health outcomes remain poor.

Some common indices of poor mental health in children include:

1. **Mood changes:** Persistent irritability, anxiety, or depression.
2. **Behavioural problems:** Aggression, non-compliance, or self-harm.
3. **Social withdrawal:** Avoidance of social interactions or relationships.
4. **Academic struggles:** Difficulty with concentration, memory, or completing tasks.
5. **Physical symptoms:** Headaches, stomach aches, or sleep disturbances.
6. **Substance abuse:** Experimentation with drugs or alcohol.
7. **Low self-esteem:** Negative self-talk, self-doubt, or lack of confidence.
8. **Difficulty with emotional regulation:** Inability to manage emotions, leading to mood swings or explosive behaviour.
9. **Trauma symptoms:** Flashbacks, nightmares, or avoidance of triggers related to a traumatic event.
10. **Suicidal thoughts or behaviours:** Expressing hopelessness or engaging in self-harming activities.

The Patterns of Children's Poor Mental Health

Children are the heritage of any family; there is no doubt that they are increasingly major victims of the consequences of becoming a burden in the area of poor mental health of any type of parental condition. This may also put the affected children at a disadvantage in numerous and often devastating ways. Mental health difficulties can manifest as either externalising or internalising problems.

The most common externalising problems, from preschool age onwards, as outlined by Tremblay et al. (2004), cited in Cavioni, Grazzani & Ornaghi (2020), include disruptive behaviour issues, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), oppositional defiant disorders, and conduct disorders. While the predominant internalising disorders include the following, as listed by Baranne & Falissard (2018), Ogundele (2018), cited in Cavioni, Grazzani & Ornaghi, 2020. It includes depression, anxiety, panic disorder, mood disorders, social phobia, specific phobias, and obsessive-compulsive disorder

Some common patterns of children's poor mental health include:

1. **Anxiety disorders:** Fears, worries, and anxiety that interfere with daily life.

2. *Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)*: Difficulty paying attention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity.
3. *Mood disorders*: Depression, bipolar disorder, and mood swings.
4. *Trauma and stress*: Reactions to physical or emotional abuse, neglect, or traumatic events.
5. *Social and relational difficulties*: Trouble making friends, social anxiety, and relationship challenges.
6. *Emotional regulation difficulties*: Trouble managing emotions, leading to mood swings and impulsive behaviours.
7. *Learning and academic struggles*: Difficulty with school performance, learning disabilities, and academic anxiety.
8. *Sleep disturbances*: Difficulty falling or staying asleep, nightmares, and sleep terrors.
9. *Substance abuse*: Experimentation with drugs, alcohol, or other harmful substances.
10. *Suicidal thoughts and behaviours*: Thoughts of self-harm or suicide attempts.

Home Factors: Parental Styles/Personality

The term 'family' is a group of persons united by marriage, blood, or adoption, interacting in social positions such as spouses, parents, and children. An ideal family is defined as a social unit comprising two parents (a man and his wife), as in the case of an intact family status, and children who are related to the parents either biologically or through adoption. The presence of father and mother in the family plays a crucial role in ensuring the proper growth and development of the child and the degree of relationship existing among the parents and their children has been found to significantly influence the well-being of the children (Amato, 2005 cited in Gbenga-Akanmu, Owojori & Famakinwa, 2019). The home is a safe place for play and nurturing, which is key for social and emotional development. The home is also where important interactions happen with parents, caregivers, friends, siblings, and others in the community (The Urban Child Institute).

Anderson (2014) believed that each child and each family are unique, with different strengths and weaknesses, different personalities and temperaments, and varying degrees of social, emotional, and economic resources. Sanders & Turner (2018) are of the view that the parent-child

relationship has a pervasive impact on children and affects many different areas of development, including language and communication, executive function and self-regulation, sibling and peer relationships, academic attainment, and mental and physical health. Homes are key settings in which to promote mental health and well-being during childhood. Home should be a place that fosters greater awareness of the world at large, an environment for spending time with children, a venue for emotional support, and an escape from unhealthy and adverse toxic environments. At the same time, the home could also be a setting where they can experience violence, abuse, and extreme emotional pressure. The United Nations Children's Fund (2021) realised that when we ignore the mental health of children, we undercut their capacity to learn, work, build meaningful relationships, and contribute to the world.

Parenting style captures two important elements of parenting:

- i. ***Parental Responsiveness***: refers to parental warmth or supportiveness. It is the extent to which parents intentionally foster individuality, self-regulation, and self-assertion by being honest and supportive of children's needs and demands.
- ii. ***Parental Demandingness***: refers to behavioural control. It is also referring to the claim parents make on children to become integrated into the family, through their supervision, disciplinary efforts and willingness to confront the child who disobeys.

Categorising parents according to whether they are high or low on parental demandingness and responsiveness creates a type of four parenting styles, and each of them reflects different naturally occurring patterns of parental values, practices, and behaviours, and a clear balance of responsiveness and demandingness. The four parenting styles include:

- i. Indulgent parents (also referred to as "permissive" or "nondirective")
- ii. Authoritarian parents (are highly demanding and directive, but not responsive)
- iii. Authoritative parents (are both demanding and responsive)
- iv. Uninvolved parents (are both low in responsiveness and demandingness)

Both authoritarian and authoritative parents place high demands on their children and expect their children to behave appropriately and obey parental rules. Authoritarian parents, however, also expect their children to accept their judgments, values, and goals without question. In contrast,

authoritative parents are more open to give and take with their children and make greater use of explanation. Overly critical, indulgent, or uninvolved parenting can negatively impact a child's self-esteem and mental health. Low levels of sensitive parenting and greater use of harsh discipline have been causally linked to the development of behavioural problems (Miner and Clarke-Stewart, 2008, cited in Ryan, O'Farrelly, and Ramchandani, 2017),

Home Factor: Family Structure

The Nelson's Deck Dictionary (1961) simply defines environment as the surrounding that affects the growth and development of any living thing. An ideal family structure should provide a template for enhancing and protecting children's physical and mental well-being. Family patterns can be monogamous (natural and stable family), polygamous, and single-parenthood (divorced or separated) families. A report from the study conducted by Anderson (2014) asserted that almost three decades of research evaluating the impact of family structure on the health and well-being of children demonstrates that children living with their married, biological parents consistently have better physical, emotional, and academic well-being.

The quality of the environment where children grow up shapes their well-being and development. Early negative experiences in homes, schools, or digital spaces, such as exposure to violence, the mental illness of a parent or other caregiver, bullying, and poverty, increase the risk of mental illness. The consequences of not addressing mental health and psychosocial development for children extend to adulthood and limit opportunities for leading fulfilling lives (WHO, 2024).

Anderson (2014) noted that the demographics of families are changing, and with that, the philosophical underpinnings of relationships are also changing. revealed that the interest in family structure and its effects on children's mental health gained momentum in the 1960s and 1970s when there was a spike in divorce rates and single-parent families (Behere, Basnet & Campbell, 2017). Disruption in family structure can lead to several adverse events impacting both the mental health of children and their parents. Not all disruptions have equal effects. More emotional and behavioural problems occur in families disrupted by divorce than compared to other types of disruptions, for example, the death of a parent. Young

children are particularly vulnerable to environmental influences, given the level of dependency in this stage of development.

Although many of the possible contributors to unpredictability in the family system are not readily modifiable (e.g., job loss, poverty), family routines represent one aspect of the family environment that is amenable to change. There exists empirical work highlighting the positive effects of family rituals and routines for optimising child health and development (Fiese et al., 2002, cited in Glynn; Davis; Luby; Baram & Sandma, 2021). Home-based risk factors include child abuse and neglect, domestic violence, poor parental mental health, parental substance misuse, poverty and unemployment, and young carers and homeless children (WHO, 2022). A few explanations of various home-based risk factors are below:

Domestic Violence

Family dynamics such as conflict, domestic violence, or substance abuse within the family can create a stressful and unstable environment, negatively impacting a child's mental health. Domestic or family violence or abuse can be physical, emotional, psychological, financial, or sexual. The child's well-being will likely be affected by disruptions to family relationships

Child Abuse and Neglect

Lack of appropriate stimulation in the early years may result in language delay, and together with inappropriate child-rearing practices, especially if characterised by neglect or inconsistency, may lead to emotional or behavioural disorders. Child maltreatment is any action causing potentially significant harm to a child or young person, which often occurs within the context of relationships of power and trust.

Behere, Basnet & Campbell (2017) reported that two-thirds of the children in the study population had been exposed to trauma, with physical abuse seen in 36% of cases. Seventy-one per cent had reported either a parent or a sibling with a psychiatric disorder. Children coming from biological families were less likely to have been exposed to trauma. Children coming from single/divorced families were less likely to have been exposed to sexual abuse, but more likely to have a diagnosis of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) compared to other types of families.

Poverty (Food Insecurity) and Unemployment

Children and young people living in poverty often lack material resources, which can affect what they eat, their participation in activities, the clothes they wear, family stress levels and optimism, where and how they live, and their access to proper healthcare and high-quality education. Poverty, financial stress, and social isolation can contribute to increased stress and mental health concerns for children.

Poor Parental Mental Health

Children may be affected by their parents' mental health issues, such as depression or anxiety, which can impact their mental well-being. Parental mental health problems may act as a stressor for children during a sensitive period because parents are central to the lives of their children and provide an essential source of social control, self-esteem, and belonging.

Divorce, Separation, or Other Family Changes

Family structure and changes such as divorce, separation, or the addition of new family members can cause uncertainty and affect a child's mental health. Childhood adversity, including divorce and impaired parenting, seems to cause both short- and long-term problems, various childhood disorders, and subsequently depression in adulthood. Dysfunctional family backgrounds and socioeconomic adversity have also been attributed to suicide in young people (Behere, Basnet & Campbell, 2017). From the study conducted by them, only 11% of children came from intact families living with biological parents, while 89% had some kind of disruption in their family structure. Two-thirds of the children in the study population had been exposed to trauma, with physical abuse seen in 36% of cases. Seventy-one per cent had reported either a parent or a sibling with a psychiatric disorder.

Impact of Divorce, Separation, or Other Family Changes on Children's Mental Health

Divorce and parental separation are damaging to children, families, the economy, and society as a whole (Anderson, 2014). When the structure of a family changes children and young people may feel: shock, loss, and rejection; anger; a strong desire to get parents back together; fear about being left alone (if one parent leaves perhaps the other one will too);

responsible – with feelings of guilt that they have done something wrong; torn between both parents; and that they have to keep both parents happy by saying negative things about the other. In addition, aggression and violence between children are increasingly prevalent concerns in schools. Children nowadays are called upon to cope with stressful situations related to academic performance, climate change, digitalisation, social inclusion (friends, family, and other communities), rapid physical change, body image, and self-esteem, among other things (Cherry et al., 2017)

Roles of Family-based Support in Promoting Children’s Mental Health

Families form the bedrock of a child’s emotional and psychological development, serving as more than just a support system (Don, 2025). A nurturing home environment offers numerous advantages for children’s growth and development. Primarily, it fosters emotional security and independence, allowing children to explore their surroundings with confidence. When children feel safe, they are more likely to engage in learning and social interactions, leading to positive behavioural outcomes. Below are some of the roles of family-based support in promoting children’s mental health:

- a) ***Emotional Support:*** In nurturing family settings, parents provide essential emotional support through unconditional love and encouragement. Creating a safe emotional space within the family is crucial for healthy child development. This helps build a child’s self-esteem and resilience.
- b) ***Positive Social Interactions:*** The family home serves as the first and most crucial classroom for developing social skills. Safe and supportive home environments foster healthy relationships, teaching children vital social skills such as empathy and conflict resolution.
- c) ***Enhanced Communication:*** Family-based support fosters open communication about emotions and mental health. Children who discuss their feelings with family members are better equipped to manage stress and anxiety.
- d) ***Cognitive Development:*** Engaging activities that involve parental involvement promote curiosity and critical thinking, key components of their educational journey.
- e) ***Creating Healthy Routines:*** Establishing clear routines and boundaries gives children a sense of stability and teaches responsibility, crucial for

self-discipline. Families play a crucial role in establishing healthy routines that shape children's lifelong habits.

- f) ***Physical Safety:*** A supportive home environment reduces risks and hazards, fostering exploration while prioritising safety, which is essential for encouraging independence.
- g) ***Accessing Healthcare Support:*** Families play a crucial role in connecting members with essential healthcare resources and support systems within their community.

Early Identification, Effective Management and Prevention Strategies of Children's Mental Health

Early identification, effective management, and prevention strategies may produce the greatest impact on people's health and well-being. Frosch, Schoppe-Sullivan, and O'Banion (2021). affirmed that a child's development is embedded within a complex system of relationships. Among the many relationships that influence children's growth and development, perhaps the most influential is the one that exists between parent and child.

Early Identification

Children's mental health is a critical area of concern, given that nearly 50% of mental disorders manifest before the age of 14. Early detection is pivotal for timely intervention and improved outcomes.

1. ***Screening Tools:*** Schools, paediatric clinics, and community centres can implement standardised screening tools to identify at-risk children. These tools assess emotional, behavioural, and social functioning.
2. ***Risk Factors:*** Understanding risk factors (e.g., family history, adverse childhood experiences) helps identify vulnerable populations.
3. ***Teacher and Parent Observations:*** Teachers and parents play a crucial role in observing changes in behaviour, mood, and academic performance.

Effective Management

Equitable access to healthcare services ensures effective management, but preventive measures are equally essential.

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1. ***Multidisciplinary Teams:*** Collaborative efforts involving psychologists, paediatricians, educators, and social workers ensure comprehensive care.
 2. ***Evidence-Based Interventions:*** Cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT) for anxiety and depression, play therapy for younger children and medication (when necessary) under close supervision.
 3. ***School-Based Support:*** Individualised Education Plans (IEPs) accommodate students with mental health challenges, and peer support programs reduce stigma and foster inclusion.

Prevention Strategies

Early prevention is regarded as a sustainable and probably cost-effective method to reduce the burden of mental disorders, especially in low-income countries where resources for care for mental disorders are low.

According to Shastri (2009), one in every five children faces a mental health issue. By investing in early identification and timely intervention, we can be more cost-effective, preventing further crises and avoiding the high expenses associated with adult treatment and rehabilitation programmes. When it comes to prevention, one must give necessary attention to genetic causes, environmental factors and the interaction between the two that can cause several childhood disorders, as some of these are preventable.

Prevention strategies are recognised as key elements for minimising the impact of any potentially serious health condition. These include:

1. Stimulating long-term and sustained improvement in children's health, by setting standards for high-quality integrated health and social care for children from before birth, right through to adulthood
2. Engaging a multi-disciplinary team or service working in a community mental health clinic or child psychiatry outpatient service, providing a specialised service for children and adolescents with more severe, complex and persistent disorders. This team can include child and adolescent psychiatrists, social workers, clinical psychologists, community psychiatric nurses, child psychotherapists, and occupational therapists.
3. Appropriate parenting styles are fundamental to caring for children's mental health. Early attachment and bonding between parents and their babies are important and need to be supported.

4. **Parenting Programmes:** Strengthen parenting skills to create nurturing environments and promote positive discipline techniques.
5. **Classroom Interventions:** Social-emotional learning (SEL) curricula enhance emotional intelligence, and mindfulness practices improve self-regulation.
6. **Community Engagement:** Awareness campaigns reduce stigma and collaborate with community organisations to provide resources.

Parenting Psychoeducation as Prevention Strategies

Motlova, Balon, Bereson, Brenner & et al (2017) define psychoeducation as the provision of systematic, relevant, comprehensive, and up-to-date information about an illness or condition, including its diagnosis and treatment. Psychoeducational programmes provide both disease-specific information, such as early recognition and management of relapse symptoms or any potential genetic implications of the illness, and general information. These include promotion of healthy lifestyle, problem-solving, communication skills training, identification of stressors in households, education of family members and primary caretakers in their amelioration. Psychoeducation is a critical first element in the provision of a comprehensive treatment plan and should not be neglected.

Parenting programmes offer a means to intercept behaviour and other mental health problems in early childhood before they become established. Programmes targeting parenting are the leading early intervention strategy for children's mental health problems. (Ryan, O'Farrelly & Ramchandani, 2017). To address the mental health and well-being of children, consideration of the family environment is vital, given the powerful impact this has on the child. A positive caregiver-child relationship and nurturing family environment are essential for healthy child development (Biglan et al., 2012, cited in Pedersen, Smallegange, Coetzee, Hartog & et al., 2019).

Possible Challenges to the Provision of Psychoeducation

Despite a strong evidence base and policy recommendations supporting the implementation of psychoeducation interventions within the mental health system, equitable access for many service users and family members has not been achieved (Higgins, Murphy, Downes, Barry, Monahan, Hevey, Kroll, Doyle & Gibbons, 2020). Certainly, the lack of adequate reimbursement for such services is a serious obstacle. Moreover, there is a speculation that the

biggest hurdle in implementing and using psychoeducation is possibly the lack of knowledge and skills in delivering it, due to a shortage of training opportunities.

Conclusion

The paper introduces us to the definition of mental health, patterns of poor children's mental health and home factors as the main causes of children's poor mental health. Mental health plays a crucial role in a child's overall well-being. Children's mental health requires a holistic approach that integrates early identification, evidence-based management, and preventive strategies. By fostering collaboration among educators, healthcare providers, and families, the stakeholders can create a supportive environment that promotes resilience and well-being. It is suggested that parenting psychoeducation will be useful in establishing the concept of home-based mental health services in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Creating a home atmosphere that welcomes and celebrates the diversity of children. A safe, comfortable, and organised home environment can promote feelings of security and stability.
2. Helping children develop resilience through teaching them social and emotional skills. This can be done through health & wellbeing education lessons,
3. Building a sense of belonging and positive relationships in the home settings, which is based on trust, safety, and security, and promoting children's wellbeing.
4. Some children may benefit from seeing a community nurse or accessing one-to-one or group-based counselling
5. It calls for commitment, communication, and action as part of a comprehensive approach to promote good mental health for every child, protect vulnerable children, and care for children facing the greatest challenges.
6. A strong support network of family, friends, and community can help children develop coping skills and resilience.
7. Government policies that will support early identification, management and prevention of children's mental health.

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